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NIZOMULMULKNING “SIYOSATNOMA” ASARIDA DAVLAT BOSHQARUVI VA YETAKCHILIKKA OID AXLOQIY QARASHLAR

THE MORAL VIEWS ON PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND LEADERSHIP IN NIZAMULMULK'S “THE POLICY”

МОРАЛЬНЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ И ЛИДЕРСТВО В КНИГЕ НИЗАМУЛЬМУЛЬКА “ПОЛИТИКА”

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada Nizomulmulkning “Siyosatnoma” asarida davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar, podshoh, Vazirlar va oddiy xizmatchilarga yuklatilgan axloqiy fazilatlar, davlat boshqaruviga oid mulohazalar muhokama qilinadi.

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the ethical views on public administration in Nizamulmulk's “the policy”, the moral qualities imposed on the King, ministers, and common servants, and considerations on public administration.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются этические взгляды на государственное управление в “Политике” Низамульмулька, моральные качества, предъявляемые к королю, министрам и простым слугам, а также соображения по государственному управлению.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR

axloq, boshqaruv, siyosat, Nizomulmulk, podshoh, qonun.

KEYWORDS

ethics, governance, politics, Nizamulmulk, King, Law.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

тика, управление, политика, Низамульмульк, король, Закон.

INTRODUCTION

Management, coordinated with morality, in its provision keeps society from Discord, emergency events, instability, stagnation. From this, the fact that the state or the governor connects his activities to morality on the basis of national values leads to an expansion of the prospects of society. After all, where there is no morality, the goal and essence of management are violated. The problem of ensuring the balance of governance and Ethics in democratic processes will depend primarily on how well the mechanisms of state governance are formed in a way that is beneficial on the basis of national values. That is, the mechanisms of government are determined by the degree of ensuring the participation of the people in political processes and in the management of power. In this, the real possibilities of citizens achieving their interests are formed. They gain the powers to participate in political processes at the level of their potential. It is this factor that leads to the Coordination of management with respect to morality. In this regard, world thinkers have formed universal, religious, scientific–theoretical views on the problems of morality, politics, power and violence for centuries. Aristotle says that “when a person's quest for Prosperity is the goal of the state, then morality and politics are also harmonious.” So, it implies the formation of management policy and ethics as a single science. Learning them and immersing them in our social life serve to elevate the spiritual life of society.

MAIN PART

Management and ethics relations have always been important. The issue has also been the focus of Eastern thinkers. Among them, Nizamulmulk (1017, Tus - 1092, Nahovand) was a Seljuk statesman Abu Ali al — Hasan ibn Ali ibn Ishaq at-Tusi. Nizamulmulk painted his "Politika" ("Siyar ul-muluk") in 1091. This work emphasized moral categories such as Justice, Integrity, correctness, and integrity, interpreting the phenomenon of politics in relation to real life. In order for any state to flourish, it must be ruled by an honest and just ruler who cares about the well-being of the people. In particular, the work

gives the following opinion: "so the state situation is such that the state and wisdom and the noble picture and custom are like a light candle. And people find their way in this light and come out of the darkness " [1]. In his work, Nizamulmulk makes a lot of demands on the sultan, all the qualities in him are the stairs that lead the state to the peak of perfection. To do this, according to Nizamulmulk, the Sultan must be a believer, that is, he must be afraid of God, because he must be responsible for everything he has done during his life. It is emphasized that he treats everything that happens in his state fairly and carefully. "It is from their charity and justice that the Kings' knowledge of the value of the blessings of Allah is revealed to the people. If the blessing of the people is graciously added, the property will be solid and will be strengthened day by day, that property will enjoy its state and peace, a good name in this universe, and it will grant mercy in this world"[1]. As can be seen from these points, the first features of the head should be justice and generosity. He is significant for his views on the choice of officials according to their moral qualities, the non-interference of those who trample justice and dishonesty in public affairs, the conduct of the state with the council in the management of the state, regular control of activities, obedience, performance and qualities. Nizamulmulk's comments, in particular, that "what is accepted as a majority will be the most rewarding and should be done as such"[1] are evidence that our ancestors paid great attention to the just procedures of State Construction. In the third season of the work, we witness that the factions that the King receives those who are oppressed two days a week, that he is righteous and good-natured have also become a current topic today.

"Ardasher (Babakon) says that if every Sultan cannot make peace and compromise his own retinue, let him know that he will bring himself only adoration and will not receive an honest good." Of course, the fact that the manager keeps those in his service uncompromising is also one of the pressing issues of the present day.

The king respects the sages and hermits with respect and follows their advice, is interested in the problems of his people, is proud and not self-rightful, but, Consulting in his important affairs, takes all the decisions made seriously and carefully. In particular, " ... to honor and honor

the hermits is a prerequisite for the King... Safyon Suriy says that the best Sultan is the one who sits with the people of the religion, and the worst of the Ulama is the one who sits with the Sultan."

The work also states that the decrees of the King, the Sultan, apply to all, which cannot be violated even by people close to the ruler. Therefore, Nizamulmulk viewed everyone as equal before law and politics. In his work "the policy", a broad reflection on public administration, the narratives, narratives, aphorisms contained in it are Nizamulmulk's responses to issues of society and state management, philosophy, ethics. The work reveals the issues of managing society and the state through a philosophical-moral approach. In Nizamulmulk's Politico-philosophical views, ensuring harmony in relations between the king (Sultan), the people (raiyyat) and the individual (citizen) was central.

The Humane King has a long rule of the state, thinks about the well-being of the people, does not use violence. "Whoever truly strives for humanity will never do bad things... Whoever loves humanity believes that there is nothing higher than it"[2], the idea was put forward in his time by philosopher Confucius. Such ideas can also be observed in Nizamulmulk. Therefore, humanity does not consist in interpersonal relations, it is a reality that also applies to the management of society and the state. Coincidentally, Nizamulmulk sometimes also interprets humanity as the way that the underlings pay homage to the adults. This interpretation is then transcribed into the relations of the king (Sultan) and the people (raiyyat), the official (servant) and The Citizen (man), the state and the individual. In any case, humanity in the management of society and the state, a call to rely on the principles of humanism - a noble aspect in the work of Nizamulmulk.

If Machiavelli argues that it is necessary for the ruler to hold the people, the state by force, using weapons [3], Nizamulmulk favors political rule. Obviously, Machiavelli advances despotism by studying the methods of the office formed in the states of ancient Rome and Greece, drawing the necessary conclusions from them. In power, various interests, aspirations collide, the support of all of them forces the king (Sultan) to beget, as a result of which he forgets about the Universal. In this context, Machiavelli believes that the ruler

is forced to use force. Nizamulmulk holds the opposite view: "the great of religion said that "Al mulku yabqā Ma'al-Kufri and lo yabqā Ma'az-Zulmi". The meaning is that "property can exist with blasphemy, and with tyranny it is doomed to destruction".

The king should not entrust to any system of leadership or leadership that is considered important in public policy, including the work of a citizen, completely stripped of his neck. In this regard, the King writes: "The King must know who is the governor of each city, how they treat the affairs of religion, fear Allah, and not be merciful. It should be said to the governor that the peace of this city and the region was handed over to him."

CONCLUSION

The main idea of the work is that the minister Nizamulmulk. the king and governors are encouraged by the justice to act in moderation, in peace and harmony, in rational control of the state, in strict rules and procedures, in order to make the official conscientious, pure, honest and believer, in order to ensure the prosperity of the country, the well-being of its people, peace and harmony.

Thus, the administration of the state performed specific functions in relation to that period. The author of the "policy book" encourages members of society to stand back on the path of loyalty, truthfulness, Justice, shows ways to act with reason and courage.

REFERENCES:

1. Низомулмулк. Сиёсатнома (Сияр улмулк). – Т.: Янги аср авлоди, 2008.
2. Хусейнов А.А. Великие этики. - М.: Республика, 1995.
3. Буттов *Александр Владимирович*. Концепция государственного управления Н. Макиавелли // Вестник Российского экономического университета им. Г.В. Плеханова. — 2016. — Вып. 6 (90). — ISSN 2413-2829
4. Kamolov D. NIZOMULMULK ASARLARIDA DAVLAT BOSHQARUVI VA YETAKCHILIKKA DOIR AXLOQIY QARASHLAR //International scientific and

practical conference. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 16-19.

5. O‘G‘LI K. D. R. Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar //ЭТИКА ВА ЭСТЕТИКАНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. – 2021.

6. Kamolov D. R. ASPECTS OF THE PHILOSOPHY OF ELEGANCE IN RELATION TO OTHER AREAS //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 12 (115)-1. – С. 1644-1647.

7. Kamolov D. R. RELATIONSHIP OF AESTHETICS WITH OTHER DISCIPLINES //Экономика и социум. – 2023. – №. 12 (115)-1. – С. 1640-1643.

8. Kamolov D., Qilicheva R. KONFUTSIY VA LEGISTLAR TA'LIMOTI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 187-192.

9. Kamolov D. et al. QADIMGI XITOIDAGI IQTISODIY FIKRLAR //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 220-225.

10. Kamolov D. ETHICS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: EXPLORING THE MORAL AND SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS OF AI IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY //SPAST Abstracts. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 02.

11. Kamolov D. GLOBALIZATION PHENOMENON AND GLOBALISM //Journal of Contemporary World Studies. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 4-9.

12. Spanov M., Kamolov D. MODERN PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF DEMOCRACY AND MORALITY IN UZBEKISTAN //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 168-172.

13. Kamolov D., Qilicheva R. SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 314-320. – 2023.

14. Kamolov D., Asrayev S. STATE POLICY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETITION IN UZBEKISTAN. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 353-361. – 2023.

15. Kamolov D., Karimqulova O. ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 199-202. – 2023.

16. Kamolov D., Ismoilova D. THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN //Science technology&Digital Finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 301-306.

17. Dostonbek K. SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY //Social science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 128-133.

18. Камолов Д. Spiritual and moral environment of society //Информатика и инженерные технологии. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 278-282.

19. Kamolov D. ATHENIAN DEMOCRACY: INDIVIDUAL AND COLLECTIVE FREEDOM //Semantic Scholar. – 2021.

20. Kamolov D. JAMIYATNING MA'NAVIY-AXLOQIY MUHITI //Social science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 78-82.